

vigor scale of 1 and high ratoon rating. Crosses involving IET6709 and IET7552 as one of the parents had high ratooning ability and ratoon yield. Among the hybrids, IET6709/IET7552 and its

reciprocal registered maximum tillers, with a ratoon vigor scale of 1 and with good ratoon rating; that resulted in high ratoon yield. ■

Influence of variety, irrigation, and N level on production of effective ratoon tillers

A. Palchamy, S. Purushothaman, and A. Kajagopal, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai, India

We studied the production of effective ratoon tillers in a field trial 1984-85 and 1985-86. Rice varieties Bhavani, Ponni, and IR20 were grown under normal management for the main crop. The

ratoon crops were grown with two irrigation schedules (5 cm water throughout the crop period and 5 cm water 1 d after the disappearance of ponded water) and four N levels (50, 75, 100, and 125 kg N/ha) in a split-plot design with three replications. Main crop plots were harvested separately, at 20-cm high, with one border row left on all sides.

Number of productive ratoon tillers had a direct bearing on productivity. More productive tillers/hill were recovered in the second year than in the first year (Table 1). ■

Table 1. Effect of variety, irrigation, and N level (50, 75, 100, 125 kg N/ha) on productive ratoon tillers/hill.

Treatment	Productive tillers (no./hill)									
	1984-85					1985-86				
	50	75	100	125	Mean	50	75	100	125	Mean
Bhavani	9.4	10.4	11.3	11.7	10.7	10.1	11.8	13.1	14.8	12.5
Ponni	6.6	7.6	8.0	8.8	7.7	9.7	11.0	13.0	13.9	11.9
IR20	5.2	5.5	5.6	6.7	5.8	9.9	11.0	12.4	13.4	11.7
Continuous Irrigation (C)	7.3	7.7	7.6	8.3	7.7	10.2	11.5	12.4	13.6	11.9
Intermittent Irrigation (I)	6.8	8.4	9.0	9.8	8.4	9.7	11.0	13.2	14.5	12.1
Bhavani-C	10.1	10.2	10.1	10.6	10.2	10.1	11.3	12.3	13.6	11.8
Bhavani-I	8.8	10.7	12.5	12.7	11.2	10.1	12.4	14.0	16.0	13.1
Ponni-C	6.7	7.5	7.6	8.0	7.5	9.3	11.4	12.7	13.8	11.8
Ponni-I	6.4	7.7	8.3	9.7	8.3	10.1	10.6	13.3	14.1	12.0
IR20-C	5.1	5.3	5.2	6.3	5.5	11.1	12.0	12.3	13.5	12.2
IR20-I	5.4	5.7	6.1	7.0	6.1	8.8	9.9	12.4	13.3	11.1
Mean	7.1	7.9	8.3	9.1		9.9	11.3	12.8	14.0	
Variety (V)				LSD						LSD
Irrigation				2.0						NS
V × C				NS						NS
Nitrogen (N)				NS						NS
V × Irrigation				0.8						0.8
N × V				NS						NS
N × Irrigation				NS						NS

Table 2. Productive tillers and yield of main and ratoon crops.

Variety	1984-85				1985-86			
	Tillers (no.)		Yield (t/ha)		Tillers (no.)		Yield (t/ha)	
	Main crop	Ratoon crop	Main crop	Ratoon crop	Main crop	Ratoon crop	Main crop	Ratoon crop
Bhavani	10.5	10.7	2.92	1.60	10.5	12.5	5.14	2.94
Ponni	7.2	7.7	2.49	0.96	9.2	11.9	5.33	1.25
IR20	4.5	5.8	3.83	0.32	11.2	11.7	5.57	0.314
LSD	1.5	2.0	0.400	0.073	1.1	ns	ns	0.158

During the first year, Bhavani had the most productive tillers/hill. This may have been due to higher carbohydrate content in the stubble crop and more regeneration capacity. Irrigation level and the interaction of varieties and irrigation level did not influence number of productive tillers. Tiller production under different N levels varied significantly, with an increase in productive tillers with increasing N.

The ratoon crop produced more productive tillers than the main crop both years (Table 2), perhaps because the ratoon crop produced tillers from the top as well as from the basal nodes. Almost all tillers formed in the ratoon crop bear panicles. ■

Growth and yield of rice varieties grown in deep water

A. R. Sharma and M. D. Reddy, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, India

We evaluated growth and yield of 13 promising rice lines developed at different research stations under deep water (up to 80 cm) at Cuttack. The photoperiod-sensitive, long-duration (170-180 d), tall (150-200 cm) cultivars and a local check were sown on 26 May at 400 seeds/m², 20-cm row spacing, and fertilized with 40 kg N, 9 kg P/ha in the furrow. The experiment was laid out in randomized complete block design with three replications.

Water started accumulating in the field at 7 d after emergence (DE) and increased rapidly to 40 cm at 25 DE. It reached maximum depths of 76 and 83 cm at 60 and 100 DE, respectively, then receded gradually to near zero at crop maturity.

Yields in general were low, because panicles/m² were few. Water stress at very early growth stages caused seedling death and adversely affected tillering. Tall cultivars (IET10084, IET10030, IET10029, IET10008, and IET10003) yielded more than 3 t/ha; relatively short cultivars (IET10006, IET9071, IET9017, IET11184, and local check Hathipanja) produced less than 2

Growth and yield attributes of rice cultivars under deep water conditions. Cuttack, India, 1988.

Variety	Cross	Flowering date (DE) ^a	Plant height at maturity (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Panicle weight (g)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
IET10084	Bashpair/Pankaj	31 Oct (159)	201	70	4.41	25.6	3.2	11.0
IET10030	Velki/Mahsuri	4 Nov (163)	197	83	3.20	25.8	3.0	8.5
IET10029	Patnai 23/Jaladhi 2	2 Nov (161)	196	75	3.44	26.4	3.0	8.7
IET10008	CN644/Patnai 23	31 Oct (159)	187	100	3.25	26.2	3.1	8.5
IET10003	Jaladhi 2/CN644	3 Nov (162)	193	70	3.82	26.7	3.0	8.5
IET10028	Jaladhi/Pankaj	1 Nov (160)	197	104	3.55	26.9	2.5	10.0
IET10009	CN644/Patnai 23	28 Oct (156)	190	75	3.00	26.6	2.2	7.7
IET9018	Selection from tall composite	1 Nov (160)	187	66	3.34	26.1	2.1	9.2
IET10027	Jaladhi/CN644	1 Nov (160)	172	79	3.00	27.3	2.0	7.8
IET10006	Pankaj/Patnai 23	1 Nov (160)	177	101	2.54	26.5	1.9	8.3
IET9071	Purelineselection	28 Oct (156)	185	79	2.91	16.1	1.9	7.8
IET9017	Selection from tall composite	30 Oct (158)	183	64	2.48	29.3	1.6	8.0
IET11184	Waihoku/CR1014	30 Oct (158)	150	81	1.86	19.9	1.5	6.8
Hathipanja (check)	—	26 Oct (154)	163	70	2.51	31.0	1.7	8.0
SE			10	9	0.60	0.5	0.4	1.3

^aDE = days after emergence.

t/ha (see table). Straw yields were much higher than grain yield and did not vary significantly among cultivars.

There was a significantly positive correlation of grain yield with plant height at maturity ($r = 0.771^{**}$) and

panicle weight ($r = 0.842^{**}$). Panicles/m² (considered to be the major yield attribute of medium-duration dwarf varieties under shallow water conditions) did not show any relationship with grain yield ($r = 0.142$ ns).

The results suggest that tall stature and panicle weight types are suitable for deepwater areas where water level increases abruptly. Work is needed to improve panicle numbers for higher productivity. ■

Stability for yield of medium-long-grain rice varieties and advanced lines

F. M. Abassi, M. A. Sagar, and A. Rabbani, Rice and PGR Programmes, National Agricultural Research Centre, Islamabad Pakistan

Cultivars JP5 and DR83 and advanced lines VT1, IR9729-63-3, DR47, Pakhal, and Kunhar were tested over nine locations. Plot size was 5 × 3 m, with 20 cm between and within rows. Twenty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 2

seedlings/hill in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Fertilizer was applied at 120-60-0 NPK kg/ha.

The slope of the regression of genotype mean on site mean yield (bi) is a measure of stability. Pakhal and IR9729-63-3 had slope (0.97 and 1.01, respectively) closest to 1.00 among all genotypes (see table). They also contributed least to genotype × environment interaction, as measured by ecovalence (wi²) and interaction variance (δi²).

In addition, the genotypes had the smallest deviation from regression on the

site index, as measured by the deviation mean square (S²d) of all genotypes. Pakhal was the most stable, followed by IR9729-63-3.

Genotypes DR47, DR83, VT1, and JP5 had regression coefficients greater than 1.0, indicating that they were more responsive under favorable environments and high fertility conditions. Kunhar, with a lower regression coefficient (b < 1.0) seemed suitable for poor environments. These cultivars should be tested across environments for a few years before their release for general cultivation. ■

Stability parameters for grain yield of medium-long-grain rice varieties and advanced lines.

Genotype	Grain yield (t/ha)				
	Mean	Wi	δi	bi	S ² d
VT1	4.6	7560101.39	1175547.81	1.16	710828.10
IR9729-63-3	5.5	4610464.15	659361.30	1.01	394547.70
DR47	4.8	6021657.15	906320.07	1.17	404016.24
Pakhal	4.8	1858478.68	177763.84	0.97	187024.95
Kunhar	5.4	4749940.25	683769.61	0.57	253366.54
DR83	5.3	5719242.00	853397.42	1.27	539474.99
JP5	4.1	4872898.51	705287.31	1.14	484018.75

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield data and yield component data from routine germplasm screening trials. Publication is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., multiple or unique resistances and tolerances, broad adaptability), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.